

THE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF EPOXY-RESIN/POWDER COMPOSITES AND OF
INDIUM/GLASS COMPOSITES FROM LIQUID HELIUM TO ROOM TEMPERATURE

F.F.T. de Araujo, K.W. Garrett and H.M. Rosenberg

The Clarendon Laboratory, University of Oxford, Oxford, U.K.

Abstract

The thermal conductivity of several series of epoxy-resin/metallic-powder composites has been measured from 1 K up to 300 K in which the influence of particle material, size, concentration and shape has been investigated. This work is a continuation of our investigations using non-metallic powder fillers (quartz, corundum, glass, diamond). The metallic powders which have been used are copper, silver, gold, aluminium, tin, lead, stainless steel and bronze. Investigations of a composite made with a metal matrix (indium) with a non-metallic powder (glass) have also been made.

The results have been analysed in terms of current theories which have been found to hold reasonably well at room temperatures. At low temperatures, however, the particle size and the acoustic mismatch between resin and powder can increase the thermal resistance to such an extent that the thermal conductivity of the composite can be lower than that of the unfilled resin. In the indium/glass composite the low temperature conductivity is controlled by the electron mean free path in the indium which is limited by the separation of the glass particles.

The results may be used to give guidance as to the thermal conductivity of a particular composite.

Introduction

A series of measurements on the thermal conductivity of epoxy-resin/non-metallic powder composites has been made by Garrett and Rosenberg (1974). This present paper describes results of another series of experiments in which the composites have metallic fillers. We have studied the thermal conductivity as a function of particle size, shape, concentration and the actual particle material.

Investigations of a composite made with a metal matrix - indium - (high conductivity) and a non-metallic filler - glass - (low conductivity) will also be discussed.

Experimental Procedure

Specimen Preparation

The matrix used in all specimens was an epoxy-resin Epikote 828 (100 parts by weight) with hardener Epikure NMA (90 parts) and accelerator BDMA (0.5 part). The specimens were prepared in the same way as described in Araujo and Rosenberg (1975).

The metallic particles were of different materials and sizes. Their shapes could be classified as follows: good spheres (copper, silver, gold, stainless steel and bronze), rounded (tin and lead), irregular (aluminium) and spongy (copper and silver).

Two different types of specimens were made for different ranges of temperature. Below liquid nitrogen temperature the specimen was in the form of a rod and the conventional steady state 'Searles bar' method was used. Heat was applied to one end of the specimen and the other end was thermally anchored to a temperature bath (liquid helium or hydrogen). The resulting temperature gradient along the specimen was measured with a differential gold + 0.03% Fe:chromel thermocouple which was connected to copper pins set into the specimens about 6 mm apart. For this method the specimens were about 25 mm long and 5 mm in diameter.

The same specimen could not be used for measurements taken at 78 K and above because the radiation losses become serious. For this range of temperature a miniature Lee's disc method was used. A 2 mm thick specimen slice was sandwiched between two copper blocks in which the heater and thermocouple contacts were embedded. A differential copper:constantan thermocouple was used in this range. The specimen was covered with aluminized Mylar strip which acted as a radiation shield.

Theory

A review of the theory of the thermal conductivity of a two-phase system is given by Meredith and Tobias (1962) and there are some more recent studies by Buyevich (1974) and Nielsen (1974). Garrett and Rosenberg (1974) includes a description of low temperature effects, and they observed that the thermal conductivity of the composite can be smaller than the values predicted by the theories. Anderson and Rauch (1970) observed a similar effect in a grease/copper-particle composite and they interpreted this as being due to an extra phonon scattering which is produced by an acoustic mismatch between the matrix and the particles (Kapitza resistance).

At temperatures above 10 K, where this thermal contact resistance is not important, the formula developed by Meredith and Tobias (1960) can predict the thermal conductivity if the filler is composed of spherical particles and for concentrations up to those approaching the maximum packing volume (~ 0.55). However, if non-spherical particles are used a formula which takes account of the shape of the particle gives better agreement with experiment. Hamilton and Crosser (1962) do consider the effect of particle shape but their theory does not include the effect of the mutual interaction between the particles and so it does not give satisfactory results at high concentrations.

Results and Discussion

Figures 1 and 2 show the thermal conductivity as a function of temperature for various resin/copper samples which contained spherical powders of diameter 100 μm and 11 μm respectively. They are representative of the type of results which have been observed with copper (5 sizes spherical and 2 sizes non-spherical), silver (2 sizes spherical and 1 size non-spherical), tin (2 sizes), aluminium (2 sizes), lead (1 size), bronze (1 size), stainless steel (1 size) and gold (1 size).

By comparing the results of figures 1 and 2 in the liquid helium range it is clear that there is a strong particle size effect. As mentioned earlier this has been explained in terms of a thermal contact resistance between the resin and the copper particles. The smaller the particle the larger the surface area for the same volume fraction and so the thermal contact resistance is increased. No size effect was observed at higher temperatures. This can be seen more clearly in figure 3, which shows the thermal conductivity as a function of concentration at different temperatures and for various sizes of spherical copper particles.

Figure 4 shows the thermal conductivity as a function of concentration at 20 K for both spherical and non-spherical particles

of copper. This shows the considerable influence of the particle shape. Both types of particles were sieved in the same way: they passed a 60 μm aperture sieve and were retained in a 40 μm aperture sieve. For the non-spherical particles the filler concentration does not exceed 30% because this was the maximum packing concentration for the spongy-like particles which were used.

On comparing our experimental results with the theory we see that for spherical particles and at temperatures where the thermal contact resistance is not significant, the Meredith and Tobias (1960) formula gives very satisfactory agreement, as is shown in figure 3.

For non-spherical particles the equation of Hamilton and Crosser (1962) gives a better agreement than that of Meredith and Tobias, but the dependence on the concentration is not quite so rapid as the experimental values (see figure 4). As we were not able to measure directly the sphericity parameter which is needed for the Hamilton and Crosser formula, we took a value which gave a fit to the experimental results at $V_f = 20\%$ and used this value to calculate the thermal conductivity at other concentrations.

At low temperatures it is still not clear how best the thermal contact resistance can be incorporated into the theory. Direct measurements of the thermal contact resistance between solid metal surfaces and the resin have been made and these will be used in calculations on the lines of those given by Anderson and Rauch (1970).

Experiments on Indium/Glass Composites

Measurements of the thermal conductivity were made on a series of specimens in which the matrix was indium metal, which is a good conductor compared with the conductivity of an epoxy-resin matrix. The filler was glass spheres (ballotini) of mean weighted diameter 1.9 μm and 45 μm . Three purities of indium were used: high purity spectrographically standardized material, commercial metal and an alloy of In + 0.5% Sn. Measurements were taken from room temperature to 4 K.

General Form of the Indium/Glass Results

Above 20 K there is no particle size effect and the general form of the results is consistent with the resin-based composites discussed in the earlier parts of this paper. The Meredith and Tobias (1960) equation holds quite well.

At 20 K and below there is a particle size effect and the

conductivity is lower for the specimens containing the smaller-sized particles. However, the size effect cannot be explained on the basis of a direct acoustic mismatch as it was in the resin-based specimens. It is due to the fact that the thermal conductivity in the indium which since it is a metal is due to the transport of heat by the electrons, - this conductivity is reduced because the electronic mean free path is limited by the actual geometrical separation of the particles. This is born out by the set of results which is shown in figure 5. Here the conductivity at 4 K is shown plotted as a function of the volume concentration of 1.9 μm particles for the three purities of indium. It will be seen that whilst at low concentrations there is a very large difference between the results for the three purities of matrix, at high conductivity they all tend to the same value. We suggest that this limiting value is a direct consequence of the restriction of the electron mean free path in all specimens due to the very short spacings between the glass particles. It is not dependent on the intrinsic conductivity of the matrix material itself. A full discussion will be given in a forthcoming paper (Garrett and Rosenberg, to be published).

Acknowledgement

This work was done during the tenure of a scholarship by F.F.T. de A. from the Conselho Nacional de Pesquisas, Brazil and Universidade Federal do Ceara, Brazil. This work was also supported by the Science Research Council.

References

- Anderson, A.C. and Rauch, R.B. (1970) J. Appl. Phys. 41, 3648-51.
- Araujo, F.F.T. de and Rosenberg, H.M. (1975). Proceedings of this conference.
- Buyevich, Y.A. (1974) Chem. Eng. Science 29, 37-48.
- Garrett, K.W. and Rosenberg, H.M. (1974) J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys. 7, 1247-58.
- Hamilton, R.L. and Crosser, O.K. (1962) Ind. Eng. Chem., Fundam. 1, 187-91.
- Meredith, R.E. and Tobias, C.W. (1960) J. Appl. Phys. 31, 1270-3.
- Meredith, R.E. and Tobias, C.W. (1962) "Advances in Electrochemistry and Electrochemical Engineering", Vol. 2, New York, Interscience Publishers p. 15-47.
- Nielsen, L.E. (1974) Ind. Eng. Chem., Fundam. 13, 17-20.

Fig.1

Thermal Conductivity(K) vs Temperature(T)

1. The thermal conductivity of epoxy-resin/copper composites from room temperature to helium temperatures for various volume concentrations V_f . The copper powder was spherical of mean volume-weighted diameter 100 μm .

Fig.2

Thermal Conductivity (K) vs Temperature (T)

2. The thermal conductivity of epoxy-resin/copper composites from room temperature to helium temperatures for various volume concentrations V_f . The copper powder was spherical of mean volume-weighted diameter 11 μ m.

Fig.3 Thermal Conductivity(K) vs Volume Concentration(V_f)
 Comparison between experiment and theory (Meredith - Tobias)

3. A comparison between the Meredith and Tobias theory and the experimental results for composites of resin + spherical copper powders of various sizes at 20 K, 78 K, 194 K and 300 K.

Fig.4 Thermal Conductivity (K) vs Volume Concentration (V_f)

4. The thermal conductivity as a function of volume concentration, V_f , for composites of resin with spherical and non-spherical particles. The heavy line is deduced from the Hamilton and Crosser equation and it is fitted to the experimental value at $V_f = 20\%$.

5. The thermal conductivity of indium/glass composites for three different purities of indium as a function of volume concentration, V_f . The glass particles were 1.9 μm diameter spheres. It will be noted that at the highest concentrations the conductivity is independent of the purity of the indium matrix.